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PASSIVE COOLING TECHNIQUES OF OLD TIMES (HAWA MAHAL)

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Abstract

Passive Cooling is a building design approach that focuses on heat gain control and heat dissipation in a building in order to improve the indoor thermal comfort with low or nil energy consumption. This approach works either by preventing heat from entering the interior (heat gain prevention) or by removing heat from the building (natural cooling). When it comes to earth friendly ideas, our ancestors from around the world had some pretty savvy concepts that we can still use in our modern world. we have to understand the techniques behind old architecture that how they kept structure cool with using natural resources and development of that techniques is going to be the way towards our golden future.

Keywords: Air Circulation, Ventilation, Lattice Work , Space Cooling, Venturi Effect.

Introduction :

Today, where we need to save our energy as much as possible, where we need to keep our environment clean from pollution or any other harmful aspect, passive cooling is the best path to be followed. Natural resources (sunlight, wind) are used in such practices and biggest advantage of natural resources is that, they are available in plenty.

Hawa mahal is one of the best example of passive cooling techniques used in old times. It consist of 953 small size windows through which air circulation is well maintained in the whole building. lattice work is also present there which helps air to pass through building with a constant rate. The lattice

provides cool air caused by the Venturi effect through the intricate pattern and thereby air conditioning the whole area during the high temperature.

Venturi Effect :

The Venturi effect is in essence the principle of pushing air through a smooth constricted passageway. By definition the principle states that as a given volume of air moves through a given area it will maintain a certain velocity.

If the same volume of air is pushed through smaller area the velocity will proportionally increase as the driving pressure attempts to push the air through.

Venturi effect is utilized in buildings for natural ventilation and passive cooling. The purposeful creation of positive and negative air pressure zones can create an increased air flow through a building or across a surface creating a cooling effect. This cooling of surfaces helps to reduce the amount of conductive energy in a material that can in turn remove heat from building.

wind chimney providing air circulation

Work Plan:

To study and understand the passive cooling techniques of hawa mahal, we have used thermocouple which is a temperature measuring instrument. We recorded readings in morning and afternoon. To show the difference between the outer temperature and inner temperature, temperature readings are taken on both sides. By comparing these temperatures, we get to know the effect of passive cooling techniques in the old structure building. In hawa mahal, venturi effect through lattice work and the 953 windows are the main reasons for the differences in temperature. The architectural design is also planned in such a way that more air can be entered in the building through the windows. This conditions also confirms that our ancestors do have knowledge of passive cooling. They know the importance and power of natural resources. We should try to learn the concept of passive cooling and develop these methods to the next level.

Window and lattice work at hawa mahal

Observations :

In Hawa Mahal, passive cooling is totally depends upon the air circulation in the building. The design of monument is so perfect that every phase of air works as the heat reluctant for building. The low wind speed are powerd by venture effect which is a technical point to be understood. As we go on the upper floars, the speed of the wind increases and therefore more cooling effect can be seen. Mr. Lal Chand Usta, the artitech of Hawa Mahal handled natural resources very cleverly. Structural design of Hawa Mahal is like bee-hive. Congested, attached sections with one another, large number of windows, lattice work are the some points which helps air to circulate through out the building and all this credit goes to the architect.

Conclusion:

“ old is gold ” this is not just a line but a lot to learn. Past time structures are planned in accordance with nature gifts. there was no A.C or fan to kept room cool. They are well aware to use nature to fulfill their need. they don't have another option but we have. today's age is technical age, we should try to co-relate our technology with the nature and this can happen only when we learn from our ancestors structures that how they maintained balance between the natural resources and man made resources. there is a vast knowledge in our past ,we just have to acquire it ,understand it ,learn it and implement it on our today's structures.

There are many more buildings like amer fort ,nahargarh fort ,samod palace ,jantar mantar where we can found passive cooling techniques.these buildings can be taken as model and on the behalf of the study of these models, we can develop new methods of execution of passive cooling techniques in our future structures. these techniques and practices can take us to the new age of structures where conservation of energy and beautification of buildings can be maintained together.

Reference:

- 1) <http://indoexpedition.com/hawamahal.html>
- 2) http://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Passive_cooling
- 3) <http://syzygyastro.hubpages.com/hub/Ancient-Earth-Friendly-Ideas-for-Modern-Times>
- 4) http://www.arch.ttu.edu/courses/2007/fall/5605_392/students/Hanlon/Venturi%20Effect_Driskill%20Hanlon.pdf
- 5) The Palace Of Wind : Hawa Mahal-BY MANISH K.,OCT.,2012
- 6) http://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Hawa_Mahal#mediaviewer/File:Hawamahal20080213-7.jpg
- 7) An exploration of the natural ventilation strategies at the world trade center Amsterdam
By Aaron william west,oct 2000,blacksberg,virginia